

CLIRAs-WND

Climate Risk Assessment – District Sankt Wendel

Phase 1 – Scoping Process – Guiding Questions – Working Document

1 Objectives

1.1 What is the objective of your CRA?

The main objective of CLIRAs-WND is to enhance climate resilience in the district of St. Wendel by developing a climate risk management plan and a local adaptation strategy based on a systematic analysis of climate risks. These measures will enable the district to better manage climate-related extreme weather events and effectively protect its citizens, with a particular focus on vulnerable groups and critical infrastructure.

1.2 What is the purpose of your CRA? What is the expected outcome? (These two questions should entail a brainstorming exercise on, among other things, most urgent risks Current and future risks, Impact on society)

Purpose:

- To systematically identify and analyse existing and future climate risks (e.g., heavy rainfall, storms, heatwaves, droughts).
- To evaluate the impacts on society, including infrastructure, emergency services, agriculture, forestry, and vulnerable groups.
- To prioritize significant and urgent risks based on vulnerability and exposure.
- To provide information to develop targeted adaptation measures and emergency preparedness plans.
- To raise awareness among stakeholders and the general public, ensuring informed action and long-term resilience.

Expected outcome:

- **A Systematic Climate Risk Assessment:** Development of a comprehensive multi-risk assessment for the St. Wendel district to identify vulnerable areas, critical infrastructures, and particularly vulnerable population groups.
- **A Climate Risk Management Plan and a Local Adaptation Strategy:** Creation of specific measures to reduce the climate vulnerability of the district, with a particular focus on disaster protection, spatial and urban planning, and the protection of critical infrastructures.
- **The Integration of Climate Risks into Municipal Planning:** Supporting the municipalities in the district in considering climate risks (e.g., heavy rainfall, heat) in spatial and urban development, urban land-use planning and infrastructure projects.
- Updated and improve emergency plan and equipment disaster protection services through more precise risk assessments and increased awareness of extreme weather events.

- **Increased Awareness and Capacity among Stakeholders and the Population:** Raising awareness and informing citizens, businesses, and agriculture and forestry about climate risks and adaptation options to strengthen individual initiative.
- **Promoting Networking and Knowledge Transfer at Regional and National Levels:** Utilizing the district's existing network to disseminate project results, enabling knowledge transfer to relevant stakeholders at the state and national levels.

Main focus of the project:

Flooding, heavy rainfall, and storm events represent the primary climate risks for the district, as evidenced by their frequent and intense occurrence within the last ten years. In addition, climate risks that are expected to intensify in the future—such as heat waves and droughts—are to be better understood in order to ensure adequate preparation and targeted adaptation. Analysing and assessing the current risks and their future development will be a focus of ClIRAs. In addition the future risks will be further addressed in phase 2.

Risk = Hazard + Exposure + Vulnerability

Current Climate Risks → will be mainly analysed in phase 1 (current risks + future development)

- A)
 - Hazard: Heavy Rainfall
 - Exposure: Population, buildings and critical infrastructure affected by heavy rainfall due to geographic conditions
 - Vulnerability: Vulnerable groups (elderly people, children, disabled etc.), not adapted buildings and critical infrastructure
- B)
 - Hazard: River Flooding
 - Exposure: Population, buildings and critical infrastructure near the rivers Blies, Theel and Nahe
 - Vulnerability: Vulnerable groups (elderly people, children, disabled etc.), not adapted buildings and critical infrastructure

Note: As there are no major rivers in the district of St. Wendel, the risk assessment did not yield any meaningful results.

- C)
 - Hazard: Storms / Wind
 - Exposure: Population, buildings and critical infrastructure affected by storms due to geographic conditions (high altitude etc.)
 - Vulnerability: Vulnerable groups (elderly people, children, disabled etc.), not adapted buildings (e.g. old roofs) and critical infrastructure

Future Climate Risks → will be further addressed in phase 2

- D)
 - Hazard: Heat
 - Exposure: Population living in hot regions / not adapted buildings; agricultural areas and forests
 - Vulnerability: Vulnerable groups (elderly people, children, disabled etc.), not adapted agricultural areas and forests

Note: Because the workflow “River Flooding” did not deliver meaningful results, the workflow “Heatwave” was already implemented in phase 1.

- E)
 - Hazard: Droughts
 - Exposure: agricultural areas and forests, critical water supply infrastructures
 - Vulnerability: not adapted agricultural areas and forests, critical water supply infrastructures (e.g. drinking water reservoir)
- F)
 - Hazard: Wildfires
 - Exposure: agricultural areas and forests; Population, buildings and tourism infrastructure (e.g. hiking trails) which could be affected by wildfires
 - Vulnerability: agricultural areas and forests

Climate change impact on different aspects of society / stakeholders:

- Focus on climate impacts on vulnerable groups (e.g. 26 % of the population is over 65; 27 % of them are in need of care). In addition, there are other vulnerable groups such as children, pregnant women and people with disabilities, some of them are reliant on care in social institutions.
- Critical infrastructure
- energy, water and waste supply and disposal
- hospitals, day-care centres, nursing homes
- relatively old building stock which are only partially adapted to climate change
- Agriculture and forestry sector
- Municipalities as main stakeholders regarding municipal planning, operating social institutions and multipliers of information to the citizens

1.3 How should your objective feed into policy and decision-making?

- **Development of a Local Climate Adaptation Strategy including adaptation measures**
 The project supports the formulation of a district-wide adaptation strategy with concrete, locally adapted measures that can be adopted by political and administrative bodies. Decision makers will be informed within the project.
 Results will be embedded into existing governance frameworks (e.g. guidelines, administrative procedures), making climate risk considerations a standard part of policy cycles.
- **Integration into Municipal and District Planning**
 The CRA results will be used to systematically integrate climate risks into spatial planning, land-use regulation, and construction approval processes across the eight municipalities of the district by conducting stakeholder workshops and creating policy briefs / planning guidelines.
- **Support for Emergency and Disaster Preparedness Plans**
 The improved climate risk knowledge will directly inform updates to emergency response plans, enabling disaster protection services to better anticipate and prepare for future events.
- **Guidance for Critical Infrastructure**
 The CRA will generate location-specific risk assessments, guiding public and private operators of essential services (e.g. hospitals, utilities) in risk-informed decision-making and investment planning.

1.4 Which limitations and boundaries may the CRA have or do you see the region confronted with in this context? E.g. worst case scenario in the context of adaptation measures?

- **Severe Financial Constraints**
 Both the district and its municipalities are in a difficult financial situation, confirmed by the Saarland State Administration Office, making it hard to fund climate adaptation independently without external support.

- **Limited Human Resources**
The public administration has very few staff available for climate-related tasks; additional personnel time must be covered through project funding.
- **Low Adaptive Capacity in Society**
A significant share of the population has low income (37% in 2021), reducing their ability to act independently on adaptation needs.
- **Limited Awareness and Risk Perception**
There is a general lack of awareness about climate risks among stakeholders and the public, including critical infrastructure operators and social institutions.
- **Non-mandatory Status of Adaptation Tasks**
Climate adaptation is not a statutory obligation for the district, meaning it does not automatically receive funding or priority in planning processes.
- **Fragmented Existing Data**
While some data on climate hazards (e.g. heavy rainfall) exist locally, there is no comprehensive, consistent multi-risk database across the district.
- **Increased Future Uncertainty**
Anticipated changes in climate conditions (e.g. more frequent extreme events) introduce uncertainty in long-term planning, especially without high-resolution local projections.

Context

1.5 How have climate hazards, risks and impacts been assessed/handled in your region until now?

Risk assessment:

- Assessment on EU/national level
 - Kopernikus: <https://atlas.climate.copernicus.eu/atlas>
 - DWD: https://www.dwd.de/DE/klimaumwelt/klimaatlas/klimaatlas_node.html
 - Climate Service Center: https://www.climate-service-center.de/products_and_publications/fact_sheets/landkreise/index.php.de
 - Monitoring Report Germany 2023: <https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/publikationen/monitoringbericht-2023>
 - Klima Wirkungs- und Risikoanalyse Deutschland: <https://www.bundesumweltministerium.de/themen/klimaanpassung/gesundheits-im-klimawandel/klimawirkungs-und-risikoanalyse-kwra-fuer-deutschland>
 - German Climate Adaptation Strategy: <https://www.bundesumweltministerium.de/themen/klimaanpassung/die-deutsche-anpassungsstrategie-an-den-klimawandel>
 - Climate Adaptation Centre: <https://zentrum-klimaanpassung.de/>
- Previous projects and initiatives have addressed individual risks (e.g. heavy rainfall).
 - [Klima SAAR project for federal state of Saarland \(heat and rain\)](#)
 - [KAN-T project for municipality of Tholey \(focus on heavy rain events\)](#)
 - [ADAPT EU project for social institutions in the district of St Wendel \(heat\)](#)
 - [Geoportal Saar offers information regarding river floods](#)
 - All municipalities of the district have their own heavy rain flooding maps:

Municipality	Link to heavy rain map
St. Wendel	Starkregengefahrenkarte für alle Ortsteile
Tholey	starkregengefahrenkarte – Gemeinde Tholey
Marpingen	Hochwasser- und Starkregenkonzept: Starkregengefahrenkarten - Gemeinde MarpingenGemeinde Marpingen
Namborn	Öffentliche Freigabe - Nextcloud - Nextcloud Namborn
Nohfelden	-
Oberthal	Dateien - Nextcloud
Freisen	-
Nonnweiler	-

- [A weather monitoring system is in place to support disaster response.](#)
- No systematic, multi-risk assessment has been carried out at district level.

Handling of risks / impact:

There is currently no disaster protection plan in place in the district of St. Wendel.

1.6 What is the governance context (policies, regulations, legal obligations, strategies, available time and resources etc.) of the assessment?

- The project aligns with Germany’s National Adaptation Strategy and the [EU Mission on Adaptation](#)
- National Law: [Bundes-Klimaanpassungsgesetz \(KAnG\)](#)
 - § 3 (2) In die vorsorgende Klimaanpassungsstrategie sind mindestens folgende Cluster und ihnen zugeordnete Handlungsfelder aufzunehmen:
 - 1. das Cluster Infrastruktur mit folgenden Handlungsfeldern:
 - a) Energieinfrastruktur,
 - b) Gebäude und
 - c) Verkehr und Verkehrsinfrastruktur,
 - 2. das Cluster Land und Landnutzung mit folgenden Handlungsfeldern:
 - a) biologische Vielfalt,
 - b) Boden,
 - c) Landwirtschaft und
 - d) Wald und Forstwirtschaft,
 - 3. das Cluster menschliche Gesundheit und Pflege,
 - 4. das Cluster Stadtentwicklung, Raumplanung und Bevölkerungsschutz mit folgenden Handlungsfeldern:
 - a) Bevölkerungs- und Katastrophenschutz,
 - b) Raumplanung und
 - c) Stadt- und Siedlungsentwicklung,
 - 5. das Cluster Wasser mit folgenden Handlungsfeldern:
 - a) Fischerei,
 - b) Küsten- und Meeresschutz und
 - c) Wasserhaushalt und Wasserwirtschaft, einschließlich Hoch- und Niedrigwasser-
risikomanagement sowie Starkregenrisikomanagement,
 - 6. das Cluster Wirtschaft mit folgenden Handlungsfeldern:

- a) Finanzwirtschaft und
 - b) Industrie und Gewerbe sowie
- 7. ein Cluster mit übergreifenden Handlungsfeldern, wie beispielsweise vulnerable Gruppen oder Arbeitsschutz.
- § 10 (6) Die Länder legen ihre landeseigenen vorsorgenden Klimaanpassungsstrategien nach Absatz 1 Satz 1 – soweit nicht bereits vorhanden – spätestens bis zum Ablauf des 31. Januar 2027 dem für Klimaanpassung zuständigen Bundesministerium vor und schreiben sie mindestens alle fünf Jahre unter Berücksichtigung aktueller wissenschaftlicher Erkenntnisse fort. Sie veröffentlichen die landeseigenen vorsorgenden Klimaanpassungsstrategien im Internet.
- Gesetz Nr. 2107 zum Klimaschutz im Saarland (Saarländisches Klimaschutzgesetz – SKSG - vom 12. Juli 2023)
 - § 4 (3) Die negativen Auswirkungen des Klimawandels sollen durch handlungsfeldspezifische und auf die jeweilige Region abgestimmte Anpassungsmaßnahmen begrenzt werden.
 - § 5 (2) Bei der Umsetzung von Klimaanpassungsmaßnahmen kommt den Handlungsfeldern menschliche Gesundheit, Bauwesen, Wasserhaushalt sowie Wasserwirtschaft, Boden, biologische Vielfalt, Land- und Forstwirtschaft sowie Verkehr und Verkehrsinfrastruktur eine besondere Bedeutung zu. Der Katastrophenschutz ist in angemessenem Umfang zu berücksichtigen.
 - § 6 (3) Die Gemeinden und Gemeindeverbände können in eigener Verantwortung eigene, an die Gegebenheiten vor Ort angepasste Klimaschutzkonzepte zur Leistung ihres Beitrags zum Klimaschutz sowie zur Klimaanpassung erstellen und fortführen
 - § 11 Das allgemeine Verständnis der Öffentlichkeit für die Ziele des Klimaschutzes sowie der Klimaanpassung sind bestmöglich zu fördern.
- Disaster protection is a legal mandate (§17 SBKG Saarland).
- Climate adaptation is not mandatory, making resource allocation difficult.

1.7 Which regional targets may be impacted by climate hazards/risk?

- Safeguarding municipal services of general interest (regulated by the welfare state principle (Art. 20 I Grundgesetz) and by § 5 KSVG - self-administration matters)
- Resilience of critical infrastructure (e.g. energy, medical facilities).
- Agricultural and forestry productivity.
- Social protection of vulnerable groups.
- Long-term planning goals in urban development and disaster prevention

1.8 How is your CRA relevant system defined?

- Spatially: District of St. Wendel (476 km²), 8 municipalities.
- Sectorally:
 - Main Focus: Disaster control, vulnerable groups, critical infrastructures, municipal planning
 - Further: Economy (Tourism, companies etc.) , Agriculture and Forestry, further sectors
- Temporally: Present to 2040–2100 horizon depending on scenario.
- Focus on interdependencies between systems (e.g. urban planning & emergency services).

1.9 Which sectors are relevant in your region and which ones may be impacted by climate risk?

- Main Focus: Disaster control, vulnerable groups, critical infrastructures, municipal planning
- Further: Economy (Tourism, companies etc.) , Agriculture and Forestry, further sectors
 - ➔ See questions 1.2 regarding risks and vulnerabilities

1.10 What is your envisaged time horizon for the CRA in terms of risk outcome(s)?

- Present
- Near-term focus: 2040

- Long-term strategic outlook: 2050 to 2100 scenarios

1.11 Where do you place value for your region? What outcome should be avoided with respect to the assigned values?

- Protection of vulnerable populations (elderly, children, disabled)
- Functionality of critical infrastructure
- Resilience of agriculture and forestry and economy
- Outcomes to avoid: loss of lives / injured people, infrastructure failure, irreversible ecosystem damage, large-scale economic losses

1.12 How bad could things plausibly get?

- Worst case scenarios:
 - Infrastructure failure due to flooding / heavy rain (causing blackout etc.)
 - Extreme weather events causing casualties and injured people (e.g. Ahrtal 2021) (flooding, heavy rain, storms, wildfires, heat)
 - Insufficient water supply due to drought
- → has to be further investigated

1.13 Where do you suspect thresholds or tipping points (environmental/economic/social)?

Environmental Tipping Points/Thresholds:

- **Water Scarcity and Quality:**
 - Prolonged periods of drought leading to a critical drop in groundwater levels and river flows (e.g., Nahe, Blies, Theel). This could reach a point where water supply for agriculture, industry, and even drinking water becomes severely constrained.
- **Forest Health and Biodiversity:**
 - Increased frequency and intensity of heatwaves and droughts leading to widespread tree stress and increased susceptibility to pests (e.g., bark beetles) and diseases. Large-scale forest dieback
- **Soil Degradation:**
 - More frequent heavy rainfall events leading to increased soil erosion, especially on agricultural lands and steep slopes, washing away fertile topsoil. → Significant and irreversible loss of soil fertility and structure

Economic Tipping Points/Thresholds:

- **Agricultural Viability:**
 - Climate-induced increased pest pressure, and reduced water availability as well as soil degradation make traditional farming practices significantly less profitable or even unfeasible for many local farmers.
- **Tourism Industry (especially around Bostalsee):**
 - Consistently high temperatures, prolonged dry spells impacting lake levels, or increased frequency of extreme weather events deter tourists from visiting, leading to a noticeable decline in visitor numbers and revenue. → A sustained downturn in tourism that leads to business closures

Social Tipping Points/Thresholds:

- **Public Health System Strain:**

- Increased frequency and intensity of extreme weather events (heatwaves, flooding) lead to a significant rise in e.g. heat-related illnesses and deaths, particularly among vulnerable populations (elderly, chronically ill), overwhelming local healthcare capacities.
- A sustained public health crisis where the local healthcare system is chronically over-stretched, leading to a decline in overall public health and well-being, and potentially increased mortality rates.
- **Insufficient Emergency Response**
 - The frequency, scale, and complexity of climate-induced disasters (e.g., flash floods in multiple areas, prolonged heatwaves combined with power outages, or widespread storm damage) begin to stretch the resources, personnel, and coordination capabilities of local disaster protection organizations (like fire departments, THW, Red Cross, etc.) to their absolute limit. Response times lengthen, and the quality of aid diminishes in certain areas.

1.14 How do you expect your hazards to change in the future?

- Increase in intensity and frequency of:
 - Heavy rainfall and flooding due to higher amount of water in the atmosphere. Long-lasting weather conditions. Higher damage from heavy rainfall after drought period (parched soils)
 - Heatwaves
 - Droughts due to longer periods without rain in summer (changed rainfall patterns)
 - Storms and wind-related events
 - Wildfires

1.15 What is your expected tolerance of risk (e.g. heat, drought, flooding) and how may it be helpful or restricting in your CRA process?

- **Flooding, Heavy Rain, and Storms: Low to Moderate Risk Tolerance**
 - St. Wendel shows a moderate risk tolerance for flooding, heavy rain, and storms. This stems from past experience with such events; disaster protection organizations are familiar with how to handle them and are equipped to a certain extent. This accumulated knowledge and existing preparedness contribute to a sense of manageability, leading to this moderate tolerance. But very extreme events are perceived with low tolerance.
 - Expected increase in heavy precipitation events → currently the main risk → focus
- **Heat, Drought, and Wildfires: Low Risk Tolerance**
 - Novelty: These extreme events, especially with their increasing intensity and frequency, are a new development for the district, with limited prior experience.
 - Inadequate Equipment: Disaster protection organizations are not sufficiently equipped for these specific challenges. There's a lack of specialized gear or expertise needed to manage widespread droughts or large-scale wildfires.
 - Lack of Adaptation: The population, buildings, agricultural/ forest areas and infrastructure are currently not adequately adapted to prolonged heat periods, water scarcity or wildfires. This includes everything from insufficient shading and cooling concepts in buildings to inadequate provisions for secure water supply during extended dry spells.

Participation and Ownership

1.16 Which key stakeholders/groups could be included in participatory processes?

Note: Stakeholder involvement is expected to evolve dynamically as results from climate risk workflows emerge.

1.17 Who are relevant representatives of known vulnerable groups or exposed areas and sectors?

- Elderly population: senior associations, care institutions
- Children and youth: daycare centers, schools, youth offices
- People with disabilities: associations and specialized care facilities
- Hospitals
- Low-income households: social welfare departments, housing associations, consumer advice center
- Rural/agricultural sector: local farming association, forestry managers
- Tourism: Tourism association (Sankt Wendeler Land Touristik)
- Exposed areas: municipalities
- Endangered infrastructure: Electricity and water supplier, wastewater and waste association

RACI matrix for all stakeholders provisionally involved:

Responsible: The person is responsible for the content of climate risk assesment (CRA) and climate adaptation activities (CAA).

Accountable: The person is responsible for financing CAA.

Consulted: The person should be heard because he or she has information, knowledge, or experience that is important for CRA and implementing CAA.

Informed: The person should be informed about CRA and CAA.

Responsible <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • District (department head) • Critical infrastructure manager • Head of social institutions • Citizens • Industry & Commerce 	Accountable <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • District • Mayor • Citizens • Industry & Commerce
Consulted <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • District Disaster Control • District Climate Protection • District Health Department • District Rural Development • District Economic Development • Municipalities • Critical Infrastructure • Social Institutions • Agriculture & Forestry • Emergency Services (Fire Department, German Red Cross, German Life Saving Association) 	Informed <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • State level Climate adaptation • District Climate protection • District Social affairs department • District Health department • District Smart cities • Municipalities • Umbrella associations of aid organizations • Social institutions • Agriculture & Forestry • Consumer protection • Citizens • Industry & Commerce

1.18 How does your legal framework allow the inclusion of key groups?

- The district can engage stakeholders through its statutory mandate in disaster control.

1.19 How is the risk assessment ownership regulated?

- The district of St. Wendel holds overall responsibility for the CRA process.
- The disaster control authority (Dirk Schäfer) leads the process, supported by the subcontractor IZES gGmbH.
- Stakeholders are involved regarding the respected risks.

1.20 How and who do you want to communicate your results to?

- Target groups for communication:
 - Local political decision-makers and municipal councils
 - Operators of critical infrastructure
 - Citizens (especially in high-risk or vulnerable areas)
 - Civil society organizations
 - Regional/national bodies (e.g. Saarland government, German District Association)
- Communication formats:
 - Stakeholder workshops and technical meetings
 - Public information events
 - Regional media coverage (print, radio, online)
 - Policy briefs and dissemination
 - Online publication of results and risk maps

2 Explore Risk

2.1 How is the scoping phase applied? Which parts of the scoping phase are relevant for the workflow and the scenario selection?

- The scoping process builds the foundation of the overall project and is especially important regarding conducting the risk workflows and stakeholder engagement.

2.2 How does the existing stakeholder knowledge come into play?

- Stakeholder Workshop end of July
- Individual stakeholder consolation if needed

Screen Risks

2.3 Which climate-related hazards and potential risks are relevant for your context?

Risk = Hazard + Exposure + Vulnerability

Current Climate Risks → will be mainly analysed in phase 1 (current risks + future development)

- A)
 - Hazard: Heavy Rainfall
 - Exposure: Population, buildings and critical infrastructure affected by heavy rainfall due to geographic conditions
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- B)
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- C)
 - Hazard: Storms / Wind
 - Exposure: Population, buildings and critical infrastructure affected by storms due to geographic conditions (high altitude etc.)
 - Vulnerability: Vulnerable groups (elderly people, children, disabled etc.), not adapted buildings (e.g. old roofs) and critical infrastructure
- D)
 - Hazard: Heat
 - Exposure: Population living in hot regions / not adapted buildings; agricultural areas and forests
 - Vulnerability: Vulnerable groups (elderly people, children, disabled etc.), not adapted agricultural areas and forests

Future Climate Risks → will be further addressed in phase 2

- E)
 - Hazard: Droughts
 - Exposure: agricultural areas and forests, critical water supply infrastructures
 - Vulnerability: not adapted agricultural areas and forests, critical water supply infrastructures (e.g. drinking water reservoir)

- F)
 - Hazard: Wildfires
 - Exposure: agricultural areas and forests; Population, buildings and tourism infrastructure (e.g. hiking trails) which could be affected by wildfires
 - Vulnerability: agricultural areas and forests

2.4 Which data or knowledge do you have on these hazards/impacts/risks? Which data, information or knowledge is further needed?

Available Data:

- Assessment on EU/national level
 - Kopernikus: <https://atlas.climate.copernicus.eu/atlas>
 - Klimafolgen Online – Potsdam Institut für Klimafolgenforschung https://www.klimafolgenonline.com/static/countries/ger/tool.html?sector_id=0&language_id=de&season=0&p_id=tmax&timeframe=30&hist=0&futsцен=0&diagram=0&displayed=0,1&abs-rel=abs&expert=0&year=2010&zoom=1&difference=false
 - DWD: https://www.dwd.de/DE/klimaumwelt/klimaatlas/klimaatlas_node.html
 - Climate Service Center: https://www.climate-service-center.de/products_and_publications/fact_sheets/landkreise/index.php.de
 - Monitoring Report Germany 2023: <https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/publikationen/monitoringbericht-2023> (Data based on DWD)
 - Klima Wirkungs- und Risikoanalyse Deutschland: <https://www.bundesumweltministerium.de/themen/klimaanpassung/gesundheits-im-klimawandel/klimawirkungs-und-risikoanalyse-kwra-fuer-deutschland> (Data based on DWD)
 - Summary current results and projects for the federal state of Saarland: <https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/themen/klima-energie/klimafolgen-anpassung/folgen-des-klimawandels/klimafolgen-deutschland/regionale-klimafolgen-im-saarland#landerspezifische-klimaänderungen>
- Previous projects and initiatives have addressed individual risks (e.g. heavy rainfall).
 - Klima SAAR project for federal state of Saarland (heat and rain)
 - Master plan Future-proof water supply in Saarland 2040
 - KAN-T project for municipality of Tholey (focus on heavy rain events)
 - Geoportal Saar offers information regarding river floods
 - All municipalities of the district have their own heavy rain flooding maps (see question 1.5)

Needed Data:

- More detailed data on different hazards.
- Spatial data regarding population, critical infrastructure, landuse etc.

Choose Workflow

2.5 Having in mind the Scoping phase and including insights from the previous sub-step of exploring risk, which workflows are relevant for your CRA? Why?

- Which climate-related hazards and potential risks are relevant for your context?
 - Phase 1:
 - Heavy rain
 - Extreme precipitation

- Heatwaves
- Wind
 - Windstorm
- Phase 2:
 - River Flooding
 - River Floods
 - Flood building damage and population exposed
 - Droughts
 - Wildfires
- Further information see question 1.2

- What is the current situation? Where is the hazard occurring? Who is being affected?
 - Heavy rain

Heavy rain events can occur throughout the district.

 - Past events: Pfingsthochwasser 2024, other heavy rain events
 - Starkes Unwetter 2022 in den Gemeinden Tholey und Nonnweiler [Starkes Unwetter im Landkreis - Feuerwehr musste mehrmals ausrücken - St. Wendeler Land Nachrichten](#)
 - Starkes Unwetter im April 2024 [Unwetter sorgt für zahlreiche Einsätze im Kreis St. Wendel - Keller und Straßen überflutet](#)
 - Starkregen im September 2024 [Feuerwehren im Dauereinsatz nach Starkregen im Landkreis St. Wendel | saarnews](#)
 - Starke Unwetter im September 2023 [Heftige Unwetter im Landkreis St. Wendel: Zahlreiche Einsätze und Feuer in Altenheim | saarnews](#)
 - River Flooding
 - Wind: Tornado in 2023
 - Gewitterfallböe in Freisen-Asweiler [SR.de: Wetterdienst bestätigt: Unwetter in Asweiler war kein Tornado](#)
 - Tornado im November 2022 in Urexweiler [Tornado im Saarland hinterlässt Bild der Verwüstung \(Videos\)](#)
 - Windstorm
 - Wildfires
 - Mehrere Waldbrände 2021 [Landkreis St. Wendel: Feuerwehr löscht mehrere Brände im Waldgebiet](#)
 - Mehrere Flächenbrände 2023 [SR.de: Mehrere Flächenbrände im Saarland](#)
 - Heat
 - Heat warning at the end of June/beginning of July 2025 [Hitzewarnung für den Landkreis St. Wendel - St. Wendeler Land Nachrichten](#)

Choose Scenario

2.6 Including Scoping considerations and taking advantage of the Technical Choices described in the conceptual Framework part, which scenarios are relevant for your workflows? Why?

- Some local data based on the RCP scenario are already available. Therefore we focus on RCP Scenarios:
 - RCP 4.5: This is a medium-emissions scenario where emissions stabilize by the end of the century. It involves some measures to limit greenhouse gas emissions, but not as drastic as RCP 2.6.
 - RCP 8.5: This is a high-emissions scenario with continued increases in greenhouse gas concentrations throughout the century. It represents a future with little to no mitigation efforts.

- We are interested in medium term and long term projections:
 - Status Quo / 2030?
 - 2050
 - 2100